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Working to get work: freelance work within the creative and cultural sectors

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Abstract

Growth in self-employment and freelance work has been substantial, both in UK and internationally, since the economic downturn of 2008. Research focuses on workers within the performing and visual arts sub sector of the creative industries (the majority of whom work freelance) to examine the range of skills required to work within these industries, how such skills are developed and constantly renewed, and the ways in which work is sourced and sustained within the context of freelance and self employment. Findings suggest that ‘working to get work’ plays a significant part in the day-to-day life of creative freelancers. This is achieved through personal and professional skills development, networking, and a facility in ways of working characterized by flexibility, adaptability, project working and resilience. It is suggested that findings could have applicability beyond the creative and cultural sector, in fact in all sectors that rely on increasing numbers of freelance workers.

Keywords

labour market; freelance employment; creative and cultural sectors; workers in the performing arts, skills development

1 Background

Within the UK ‘self-employment accounts for nearly half of all jobs created since the economic downturn of 2008...it may not be long before freelancers, sole-traders and micro-entrepreneurs outnumber the public sector workforce’ (RSA, 2017). The UK Office for National Statistics (ONS, 2018) reported that the UK labour market had seen significant growth in the numbers of self-employed workers from 2008. By 2017 self-employed workers constituted 15.1% of the UK labour force. Tomlinson and Corlett (2017) reported that self-employment (either as a primary or secondary job) accounted for 45% of employment growth between Spring 2008 and February 2017. Further examples of the proliferation of self-employment and freelance work can be found elsewhere, for example Singapore (Karmel et al., 2013), USA (Hipple and Hammond, 2016) and Germany (Eurofound, 2009).

Freelance, and temporary contracted, labour is being used to supplant permanent ‘on payroll’ staff and functions once carried out ‘in-house’ for example, cleaning, catering, even finance and HR functions are being outsourced to other providers. Alongside this, an increasing number of school/college leavers, particularly those with few or no qualifications, are susceptible to the fragmentation of jobs, zero-hours contracts and low paid work (IER, 2017; Tomlinson and Corlett, *ibid*). The reality of the workplace is increasingly characterised by precarity (Fleming, 2017; Standing, 2014), short-term, or zero hours contracts, temporary work and self-employment. A ‘job for life’ is no longer the experience of most workers.

‘Now a typical worker – more likely to be a woman – can anticipate having nine employers before reaching the age of 30’ (Standing, *ibid.* 62).

An area of the economy which is increasingly important and where self-employment is commonplace is the creative and cultural sector (a diverse sector offering a wide range of occupations across art and design, performing arts, fashion, media, IT, marketing and publishing). In terms of employment, it accounts for around 2.8 million jobs. Between 2013 and 2014, jobs in the sector increased by 5% compared with an increase of 2.1% for the wider UK economy (DCMS 2016). In 2014, the export of services from the creative industries was valued at £19.8 billion, up 10.9% on the previous year and accounting for 9% of the UK’s total export services in that year (DCMS 2016). The recent Bazalgette Review of the Creative Industries predicts that the creative industries could be worth £128.4 billion to the UK economy by 2025 and help to create up to one million jobs by 2030 (Bazalgette, 2017).

2 Research approach

The data we draw upon are primarily derived from ongoing ethnographic research into work in the creative sector, particularly those working across dance, music, theatre, film and television either in performing or technician roles. Sampling has been purposive (Cohen and Manion, 1994) that is, drawn from specific communities of interest and their typicality (freelance workers within the creative sector, particularly performing arts). This is augmented by snowball sampling: informants identifying others who might qualify for inclusion (Cohen and Manion, *ibid.*). Participant observation in the field, including at rehearsals, studios, live events and interaction through social media has enriched the interview data. There is significant cross-over amongst respondents as many freelance workers find employment across a range of sub-sectors within the creative industries and also in a range of other industries and sectors such as education. Furthermore, it is not uncommon for these freelance workers to also develop their own enterprises as they seek to gain sufficient, flexible employment and income to enable them to pursue their chosen career.

3 Findings

Freelance workers within the sector deploy a range of skills in order to maintain employment. These include practical elements such as physical and technical skills, social and marketing skills, skills in emotional intelligence and reciprocity and the creative skills to develop and create work through entrepreneurial enterprises.

3.1 Practical skills

On a practical level workers reported having to work to maintain their own practical skills in order to remain relevant in the labour market. These included camera men and sound designers buying new equipment and /or software and learning how to use it via workshops or through YouTube, musicians buying and using emerging and changing software packages (Choi and Burnes, 2013; Banks, 2006), dancers taking classes in new dance styles to ensure that they are prepared for any audition (Ashton and Ashton, 2016).

In addition to skills that are directly related to their freelance work these workers also gained other practical skills in order to supplement their income. These varied from plumbing to make-up artistry and dog grooming. Whilst some of these skills were gained through external training (largely self-funded), others were gained informally. For example, one performer began working backstage and became sufficiently proficient to work across both sound and lighting in London’s West End theatres. Identifying the skills required and knowing how to gain such skills within limited financial means is a significant strength of all these workers. They conformed to Knowles (1975:18) conceptualisation of ‘self-directed

learners' that is: 'taking initiative in identifying learning needs, setting goals, identifying learning resources (material and human), implementing strategies and evaluating outcomes'.

3.2 Social and Marketing skills

Social networks are crucial to freelance workers because this is the primary source of gaining work, or hearing about work, or accessing key gatekeepers. These are maintained online through various social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and Instagram, but also in person through events and informal meetings. This also enables workers to keep updated on 'live' information such as, who is hiring and for what. The wider the network the greater the range of possibilities, but maintaining such a range of networks takes time, effort and skill.

Marketing and promotion are also central to freelance work. Again, this is achieved at the workers' expense. Performers and choreographers have to keep their 'headshots' and 'showreels' up to date and of high quality in order to pitch for work. The use of social media for self-promotion is increasingly important. Some respondents reported having received social media marketing workshops during their vocational training; others had paid to attend workshops on effective social media marketing and management as working professionals. An awareness of the needs and norms of the industry is also vital for the success of any marketing strategy or engagement.

3.3 Emotional Intelligence and Reciprocity

Social norms are embedded in wider professional practices such as arriving early to work, learning to work quickly as part of a team and taking responsibility for one's own work within a project. Respondents reported the importance of resilience when facing 'knock-backs' (unsuccessful auditions) and how to address issues quickly and effectively. Social and emotional skills included the ability to adapt behaviours according to the environment "becoming a chameleon that can blend in", even in the most novel context.

A further aspect of this is the way in which workers behave reciprocally, even sacrificing work for another worker if they feel their need is greater. This was particularly demonstrated by musicians, but there were elements of this reciprocity across the sectors. People unable to accept jobs offered through their networks would recommend each other despite the intensely competitive labour market that marks the sector. In this respect traditional notions of competition and the competitive nature of these industries is tempered by the mutual reliance on your fellow workers to gain and maintain employment.

4 Discussion

The findings point to a range of skills that are transferable and increasingly coveted in other employment contexts. We found that there was considerable depth in the skills gained; this went beyond anticipated skills such as team work, working with other professionals and working independently. Tacit skills included an ability to work flexibly across a range of areas, identify their own skills gaps and seek out opportunities to develop these skills with an understanding of how and why they are relevant within their industry and the labour market.

Another range of skills displayed by these creative workers was the ability to market themselves and their work appropriately and network effectively in order to seek out and create opportunities. Networks were used to develop creative solutions to a range of issues. These might be issues faced as individuals, such as finding flexible solutions to ensure some financial stability, or solutions to problems within a particular work context. In short they engage in a variety of activities drawing upon a range of skills 'working to get work'.

These skills are vital to this group and enable them to find sufficient work, often from a range of sources, in order to maintain and develop themselves in a sector that is marked by

precarity and a dynamic pace of development (Bazalgette, 2017; Lahiff and Guile, 2016)). Such skills are increasingly important in the UK labour market and therefore the UK economy more broadly.

5 Conclusion

Beyond the realms of freelance and self-employment such skills are also linked to the project based modes of production that are prevalent in many sectors. This type of production offers flexibility and speed in innovation, making it increasingly popular as a way to organize work within larger organisations (Whitley, 2006; Hobday, 2000). Tech companies such as Google and Facebook are the most obvious exponents of this approach but it is becoming increasingly popular in the organization of work outside of the creative and tech sectors (Sydow et al., 2004; DeFillippi, 2002).

The proclivity of freelance workers in the sector to innovate and find creative solutions through collaboration and networking, and to find, create and develop diverse links was central to their abilities to gain and maintain employment. These skills were vital to their success as they ‘worked to get work’ rather than passively waiting for opportunities to come to them. We suggest that the need to develop and sustain such skills is not restricted to those working within the creative sector but could have a wider applicability for any sector where freelance employment is ubiquitous.

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Notes

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